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Phytochemical Study of *Rumex acetosa* Linn.

P. N. VARMA, D. R. LOHAR and A. K. SATSANGI

Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia Laboratory,
Ghaziabad-201 002Manuscript received 22 September 1981, revised 18
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RUMEX acetosa Linn. (Polygonaceae) has been investigated earlier and oxalic, fumaric, α -ketoglutaric, succinic, glycolic, aconitic, citric and isocitric acids, napsoid, a naphthalene glucoside², chrysophanic acid, chrysophanein have been isolated^{3,4}. We have reinvestigated the chemical constituents of the leaves, since these are used in homoeopathy.

Powdered leaves (50 g) were soaked in 60% ethanol (500 ml) for 24 hr. The alcohol was decanted and the solvent removed. The remaining concentrate, thus obtained, was extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (A) was concentrated on water bath to 10 ml. To the aqueous layer, sulphuric acid (6 N; 50 ml) was added and refluxed for 30 min. After cooling, it was again extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (B) was also concentrated to 10 ml. This was washed with distilled water (25 \times 2 ml) and the acid free chloroform layer was chromatographed.

The chloroform extracts A and B were chromatographed over silica gel G plate (200 μ ; 10 \times 20 cm) using benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2 v/v) as solvent. The plates were sprayed with 0.5% methanolic magnesium acetate. Three pink coloured spots appeared at R_f 0.60, 0.75 and 0.98 in case of the extract 'A'.

The three yellow coloured compounds were isolated from chloroform extract A by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel G and were characterized as chrysophanol, 1,8-dihydroxy anthraquinone and 1,8-dihydroxy 3-hydroxymethyl anthra-

quinone (aloe-emodin), respectively by comparison with the data (uv, ir) available in literature^{5,6}.

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Chemical Constituents of *Physalis peruviana* RootsMAHENDRA SAHAI* and PARTHA NEOGI¹Department of Organic Chemistry, The Weizmann Institute
of Science, Rehovot, IsraelManuscript received 23 October 1982, accepted
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PHYSALIS peruviana Linn. (Solanaceae) is cultivated throughout India for its edible berries¹. The plant finds a variety of medicinal use in traditional system of medicine². The leaves of this plant yielded a number of withanolides³⁻⁷, physalin A⁸, perulactone⁹ and perulactone B⁹ while its roots yielded several new withanolides^{6,10} and tropane and secotropane alkaloids¹¹⁻¹⁴. The present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol, physalolactone, 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside and rutin from the roots of this plant.

Experimental

Air-dried and powdered roots (2 kg) of *P. peruviana* were extracted with ethanol (95%). The ethanol extract was concentrated (1.0 l) and diluted with equal volume of water and then extracted successively with petrol (60-80°) and diethyl ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, evaporated to dryness and chromatographed over silica gel column.

Results and Discussion

β -Sitosterol : Elution of the column with benzene yielded β -sitosterol, shining needles, m.p. 136°

*Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.